

EFFECT OF COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES ON HOUSEHOLDS' EMPOWERMENT: THE CASE OF GASABO DISTRICT, RWANDA

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Abstract:

This paper aims to assess the effect of Community Development Programmes on households' empowerment in Gasabo District of Kigali City, Rwanda. The level and the speed of economic growth in Rwanda are determined largely by community development programmes. Although, to achieve the goals of economic development in long run postulated in the vision 2020, several programmes have been implemented to improve families' livelihoods mainly Rwandans' in rural areas. The study sample size of households of 322 were employed. This research was employed both quantitative and qualitative techniques in data collection process, analysis presentation and discussion of findings. Basis on descriptive method employed, the findings show that the mean household size is 4.371 approximated to 4 persons per household with a standard deviation of 1.791 approximated to 2. The smallest family had 1 member and the largest had 11 members. This implies that households with big family size were more likely to participate in community development programmes to increase their income. Based on household revenues from agriculture production, handcraft and income from salaried employees among others, the results show also that total annual expenditure is less than total annual income. The study argues that households who had participated in any community development programme had increased their livelihoods. Based on the empirical results, the study is recommending the local government, have to give consideration to community development programmes, as well as encourage family planning both urban and rural areas so as to serve as rooter of social economic development and must also enhance their management ability and bring effort to reach the poor people in order to eradicate poverty and promote the welfare of the society.

Index Terms: Effects, Community Development Programmes, Households, Empowerment & Rwanda

1. Introduction:

The most fundamental rationale for creating Local Government anywhere in the over the World is to employ it to take responsibility for the development of the area directly and also contribute indirectly to the development of the nation. It also entails improvement in the socio-economic and technological systems that operate in a given country (Agbamu, 2006).

Rwanda is very densely populous sub-Saharan 'country. Twenty years after Rwanda Genocide, the country has turned into a growing success story and unity and reconciliation have been consolidated, strengthening good governance in the middle term (Eduard & Diabate, 2015). Recently, rehabilitation, reconstruction were made, the country has realisations in setting a trend of high economic growth remarkable as evidence by its annual average Gross Domestic (GDP) growth of 6.4 percent between 2001 and 2006. This high economic growth has been on the factors that contributed to

the reduction of the incidence of poverty from 60.4 percent to 56.6 percent during the same period.

Concerning the promotion of gender equality and empowerment of women, primary achievement comprises: 1) the reduction of poverty among Female Head Households from 66.3 percent in 2001 to 60.2 percent in 2006 still than the national rate; 2) gender parity in primary education has been achieved; 3) Gender equality in decision-making policy 64 percent from women representative in parliament.

Community Development in Rwanda can be traced back to the 1970s, but top-down and centralized approach limited initial efforts. The history of Rwanda shows that, much as the population is willing to work but has never sufficiently participated in its own development.

Government of Rwanda through the Local Government has played a central role in the exercise of community development work. It promoted self-reliance through the programmes where individual farmers and farmers 'associations increased their production levels (MINALOC, 2011).

Community development is the process of increasing the strength and effectiveness of communities, improving people's quality of life and enabling people to participate in decision making to achieve greater long control over their lives. Archer&al., (1984), states that the overall aim of community development is to work together in a situation in which everyone believes that her or his values are respected in the process of striving to reach outcomes that are benefit to all. Academics, policymakers, researchers and community development practitioners employ various models of community development, self-help, government planning, and social capital. Bullen (2007) discusses two fundamental models of community development that are particularly relevant. One is the community capitals framework and second is the community empowerment model. Cavaye (2002) argues that developing government's role in community development involves in creating a vehicle for developing local personal relationships and bottom-up community involvement. Government should indeed deliver excellent services that efficiently satisfy population. The public are clearly demanding greater service delivery particularly in rural areas. ADM (2003), offers that community development is seen to address a deficit in democratic access affecting marginalized groups, the starting point for achieving inclusion and equality for excluded groups must be the excluded themselves, Maxwell (2003), deals that this reflects the belief that there is more to exclusion than simple financial metrics; rights, influence, freedom, status and dignity are all components of well-being. Furthermore, Petts (2005), states that community development with various burgeoning critical theories of democracy that promote inclusion and deliberation as a means of power redistributions the spreading of power is a goal in itself, whatever results this leads to in poverty terms. Community development has a focus on process as well as outcomes. Phillips and Pittman (2009), strengthened these views that community development collective action in which local decision-makers and residents work together to improve the critical social, economic and as well as environment conditions in their communities.

Narayan explains human capital as the norms and social relations embedded in the social structures of society that enable people to coordinate action and to achieve desired goals. This is the human resource "people" account. It comprises leadership capabilities, knowledge, wisdom, information, and skills possessed by the people who live in the community. He goes to explain that social capital is the key networking account. It concludes the bonds between and among family and friends, the people we know and this has been employed by the World Bank as a key to alleviate poverty

(Narayan, 1999). Shared of the research on social capital studies its occurrence and effect on individuals, and as the sum of each individual's norms and social relations.

Political capital is the capacity to move a community norms and values into standards, rules, and regulations that determine among other things, the distribution of and access to all the other capitals. This explanation signifies power and our connections to the people who have power.

While Financial Capital comprises the resources related to money and access to funding such as savings, credit, grants, tax and revenue etc,

While another dimension is Building Capital which defines the building and infrastructure account. It comprises houses, schools, businesses, roads, transportation systems, communication systems etc, and makes them accessible to all households participate and non-participate in community development (Lockwood, Dvidson, Curtis, Stratford and Griffith, 2010).

Based on statement of the following authors (Walkinson, 1999; Luloff and Swanson, 1995; Luloff and Brigger, 2003). All communities have many distinct grouping of people so that these groups, numbers people act to achieve various interests, andgoals. Green and Haines (2012) State that bringing together these local assets allow for the maximization of local resources and community development programmes.

Results show that Rwanda has made remarkable progress in a number of areas, but that challenges remain. There are challenges of mobilizing adequate financial resources, poor infrastructure, and still weak human resource base continue to limit the achievement of set objectives. The challenge it is to change the mind-set and develop a results oriented management culture and reduce the dependence model.

2. Methodology:

2.1. Data Collection Methods:

The present paper is based on study carried out in Gasabo District the year 2015. Household heads selection were purposive to ensure that interviews are conducted to those in participation and non-participation in community development programmes. The three sectors of Gasabo District were covered with cross section data from a sample of 322 households. The primary data were collected using structured questionnaire administered on face-to face interview arrangement (Saunders et al.2000). Though, secondary data were also used for the purpose of collecting background information supporting the research. The study employed survey design using descriptive statistics to analyze quantitative data (Leedy and Ormrod, 2001).

3. Results and Discussion:

Descriptive Statistics:

This study presents the empirical data from Gasabo Distract in three sectors on effect of Community Development Programmes on households' empowerment in Rwanda. The presentation discussion and assessment of the data were carried out in relation to the objective of the study and in comparison, with the quoted in secondary sources. To present the findings, the study has employed tables and figures by using qualitative and quantitative methods were adopted (Patton, 1990).

HH Size, Total Annual Income and Total Annual Expenditure of Household in Gasabo District:

Table 1: Minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of HH Size, Total annually income and Total annually expenditure n=322

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev.
HHSize	1	11	4.371	1.791
Total Annual Income	152,000	7,800,000	1,082,567.123	1,227,570.177

Total Annual Expenditure	138,000	5,865,600	895,236.152	762,664.201
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Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 1 show that the mean household size was 4.371 approximated to 4 persons per household with a standard deviation of 1.791 approximated to 2. The smallest family had 1 member and the largest had 11 members. This suggests that households with big family size were more likely to participate in community development programmes to increase their income. The table 1 shows also that the mean annual household income was 1,082,567.123 Rwandan francs, approximated to 1,388 USD and based on the household revenues from agriculture production, handicraft, and revenue from salaried employees, among others and standard deviation was 1,227,570.177 Rwandan francs, approximated to 1,574 USD while the mean annual household expenditure was 895,236.152 Rwandan francs, approximated to 1,148 USD and standard deviation was 762,664.201 Rwandan francs, approximated to 978 USD. From these results, the total annual expenditure is less than the total annual income. It points out that households who had participated in any community development programme had increased their livelihoods.

Effect of Community Development Programmes on Household in Gasabo District:

The Figure1 indicates the effect of community development programmes on household in Gasabo District

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The results show that majority of respondents for what indicated to benefit from community development programmes 32.4 percent indicated income increased, 25.1 percent indicated paying school fees for children, 16.5 percent indicated farm income increased, 10 percent indicated paying health insurance, 8.7 percent indicated access to

credit from financial institutions, 4.1 indicated starting business and while 3.2 percent indicated opportunity for new skills.

Women Empowerment in Community Development in Gasabo District:

Table below reveals the awareness of respondents for women empowerment in community development in Gasabo District. Respondents were asked most of them 42.5 percent women take active role in social economic development, 28.3 percent responded women participate in politics and decision-making, 26.7 percent women are still regarded as second class citizens while 2.5 percent were others.

Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Women take active role in social economic development	137	42.5
Women are still regarded as second class citizens	42.5	26.7
Women participate in politics and decision-making	91	28.3
Other	8	2.5
Total	322	100

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The table above presents distribution of challenges households facing in community development programmes, majority 35.4 percent responded lack of funds, 19.6 percent responded lack of communication, 15.5 percent responded lack of credit, 14.3 percent responded lack of human social capital, 14 percent responded inadequate of service delivery, while 1.2 percent responded climate change.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation:

In this study, we mainly depend upon the primary data sources. We have also undertaken a brief of global secondly data and pointed on some closely related material of relevance. This places community development programmes on households 'empowerment. Gasabo District in three sectors namely Jali, Jabana and Gatsata was a study of where primary data concerning the purpose of the study to the study objective has been collected. The study explores the ways in which the community development programmes has empowered and affected areas and challenges facing them as well.

It was revealed that there were different ways in which community development programmes affect the households 'empowerment. Our empirical analysis demonstrates that 64.4 percent of respondents agreed that households were accessed to credit, benefit from financial institutions, total annual income and total annual expenditures have positive and significant effect on community development programmes on households 'empowerment. The results also conclude that community development programmes have a significant and positive effect on households' empowerment; 42.5percent women take active role in social economic development. Hence, the study finds out that lack of funds, lack of communication, as well as lack of human capital reducing better condition of living, better income, better welfare, and self-reliance.

This implies that policies aiming for sustainable community development and inclusive growth must address important critical areas as well as monitoring and evaluation. The study also is recommending the local government, have to give consideration to community development programmes, to alleviate poverty and must also enhance their management ability and bring effort to reach the poor people in order to eradicate poverty and promote the welfare of the society.

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